

ITSERR – WP7

DELIVERABLE 7.1.1

WHITEPAPER ON CORPUS PRE-PROCESSING

Document reference: ITSERR- WP7- DELIVERABLE 7.1.1 – Whitepaper on
Corpus pre-processing

Version number: 02.00

Status: FINAL

Last revision date: 03/12/2025 by:Laura Righi
Ilaria Sabbatini

Verification date: 02/12/2025 by: Board

Approval date: DD/MM/YYYY by:MUR

Subject: IR0000014 – ITSERR
TITLE FROM FILE SUMMARY PROPERTIES

Filename: ITSERR_WP7_deliverable7.1.1_FINAL.docx

Change history

Version Number	Date	Status	Summary of main or important changes
00.01		WORKING	Working version
01.00		DRAFT	Complete revision of the document after ITSERR Board review
02.00		FINAL	Finalisation

Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
All ITSERR team members	ITSERR	

List of tables

Table 1	10
Table 2: The most popular OCR software	29
Table 3: HTR handwritten text recognition for historical texts	30
Table 4: Overview of the analysed Optical Recognition Systems	31

List of figures

Figure 1: From printed editions to Plain Text	11
Figure 2: Layout Analysis.....	13
Figure 3: Two types of regesta editions	15
Figure 4: The first model of data collection on papal regesta	16
Figure 5: The second model of data collection on papal regesta	17
Figure 6: The transformation through an OCR System	19
Figure 7: Typographical critical elements	20
Figure 8: Examples of noise	22
Figure 9: The three phases of OCR-HTR system	24
Figure 10: Transkribus interface.....	27
Figure 11: OCR4all Interface	28
Figure 12: Rescribe Interface	28
Figure 13: Escriptorium Interface	29

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
1.1. Objectives	5
1.2. Document Scope	6
1.3. State of the Art.....	7
2. Corpus Analysis and Methodological Approach for REVER	11
2.1. Reverse Regesta and the Need for Text Recognition	11
2.2. Field of Study: paleography and diplomatics	12
2.3. Corpus definition and pre-processing methodology.....	14
3. Analysis of OCR and HTR existing tools	19
3.1. What is an Optical Character Recognition system	19
3.2. What is an Handwritten Text Recognition Systems	20
3.3. Basic OCR-HTR glossary	21
4. Common Elements of OCR and HTR Systems.....	23
4.1. Core Phases of OCR/HTR Systems.....	23
4.2. Operational Phases of OCR/HTR Software	23
4.3. Manual and Automatic Workflow.....	25
5. Analysis of OCR-HTR systems: features, capabilities, and key criteria.....	27
5.1. Tested Softwares.....	27
5.2. The choice the Right OCR-HTR.....	30
5.3. Considered criteria for evaluation	30
6. Results.....	32
7. Acronyms.....	33

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

The main goal of the Work Package 7 - REVER, Reverse Regesta is the creation of a tool based on Artificial Intelligence for the summarization of medieval documents, and especially of pontifical documents. The decision to use this system to organize, index, and summarise medieval documents through the use of generative AI is based on the integration of various scientific needs, which will be the subject of in-depth discussion and testing. To develop a new automatized organizational process specifically created for historical documents, we chose to focus on the activity of automatic summarization grounding on an established and scientifically consolidated methodology - namely the creation of regesta, improved by scholars starting from the 19th century.

The work of this WP starts from the observation of a scientific need coming from the scholars studying medieval charters: the need to explore specific topics, historical figures, or places, even with a comparative or a *longue durée* perspective, within a large *corpus* of sources.

For the study of the Middle Ages, this is the case with the large amount of documentation produced by royal or papal chanceries. Corpora which are still today dispersed, preserved in different libraries and archives, which are geographically distant and differently organized, and thus not easily accessible for scholars. Due to the difficulties in access and consultation, for the scholars it is even more important in this case to correctly extract, record, and organize the data contained in these sources and make them navigable for each specific research project.

The methodologies and tools to index and organize Medieval archival sources have not, however, seen in the last decades a great development, neither methodologically, nor technologically. Until now, most research on medieval papal documents still relies on ancient indexes and collections of summaries, edited by scholars in the 19th century. Among the various tools and methodologies adopted by scholars working on the history of the medieval Latin Church, the edition of *regesta* collections has been one of the most durable.

Indeed, until now, *Regesta* have been produced mostly in printed collections and focusing almost exclusively on the documents produced by sovereigns, emperors, and popes. The compilation of a *regestum* requires an important effort in terms of time and resources and, moreover, these collections have only been updated, corrected, and supplemented on rare occasions. For the same reason, there is a scarcity of collections of *regesta* that have been compiled for documents that are less well-known and of

lesser importance regarding, for example, those historical figures or local institutions that are less prominent in the historical record. Thus, leaving behind – and sometimes forgotten in the archives – a large number of mediaeval sources.

Only in recent years, *the regesta* collections started to appear online. The most important digital initiative related to *regesta* is undoubtedly the database *Regesta Imperii*, which focuses on the documents issued by German mediaeval rulers. While related to our corpus, we can notice three ongoing projects, which are publishing online regesta of papal documents: *Regesta Pontificum Romanorum Online* [<https://www.papsturkunden.de/EditMOM/home.do>]; *Aposcripta* [<https://aposcripta.hypotheses.org/>]; and *BREPOLiS' Ut per litteras apostolicas Database* [<https://about.brepolis.net/ut-per-litteras-apostolicas-papal-letters-litpa/>]. These projects aim at publishing online ancient collections, but none of those is publishing for now new *regesta*. On one hand, this shows us the reliability of ancient *regesta* collections, the remaking of which is not seen as a priority for the advancement of the discipline. But, at the same time, we must not forget that the creation of a new *regestum* requires relevant amounts of time, incompatible with the timelines of modern research.

On the contrary, REVER wants to collect a broad corpus of historical data – namely the already existing *regesta* and their linked extended text – to train ITSERR's Latin Language Model (LM) specifically on the summarization of mediaeval pontifical documents and, thus, produce new *regesta*.

Therefore, REVER aims is not creating another database of sources and *regesta* but rather providing a tool for scholars to build their own database, from time to time, according to their scientific needs.

1.2. Document Scope

The objective of Deliverable 1 is to present the work conducted for the definition and preparation of a specific medieval corpus for the design of a tool for automatic text summarisation.

This whitepaper contains thus a report of the sources that have been selected, analysed, and pre-processed by the WP to be used for the development of REVER.

The process and the results are presented according to the experience developed with the case-study corpus, however, they are also intended to be applicable to other corpora: they are therefore not corpus-specific, but rather software-specific, and can be updated throughout the work of the WP.

1.3. State of the Art

A vast majority of cultural heritage and historical data comes in the form of digitised Document Images. Among those, *regesta* collections are a valuable source of information for scholars of many different fields of humanities and social sciences (e.g. history, religious studies, linguistic and literary studies, etc.). Indeed, a *regesta* collection is a catalogue of summaries arranged in chronological order. Each *regestum* is the summary of a historical document; and in some cases, it is the sole source of information about the full-length document it summarises (henceforth the extended text). The *regestum* is a summary of the main content of a document, which in the case of *Reverse Regesta* concerns the acts issued by the Pope of the Catholic Church. The *regesta* provides an overview of the document, serving both a summarising and cataloguing function, which makes the information contained in the original document more accessible and easier to consult, allowing for the quick retrieval of specific data. While palaeography an indispensable tool for the accurate transcription and evaluation of pontifical regesta, diplomatics is an invaluable resource for the interpretation of official acts exchanged between political entities, sovereigns, and governments. For the *Reverse Regesta* project, the research field of papal diplomatic which concerns the documents produced by the papal chancery, is of particular importance. Thanks to the work of paleographers, archivists, and librarians, documents of great historical and cultural value can be preserved and made available to the public. The utility of these tools for historical research is evident, particularly in studies concerning the papacy, the Catholic Church, and more generally on religious studies.

A *regestum* is – both visually and textually – a strongly structured summary of a document, created following a consolidated methodology, involving: a) the extraction of information from specific sections of the extended text; and b) the translation and codification of the selected information into a language shared by the community of scholars. *Regesta* are documents whose layout is as important as the content since the structure helps to correctly correlate the contents. In this sense, *regesta* are visually rich documents. They are at the same time new collections of sources and organized data related to a vast range of topics, places, and individuals; and indexing tools for scholars to find the historical documents preserved by archives all around the world.

This methodology to summarise historical documents has been specifically created and used to collect, index, and summarise vast corpora of mediaeval documents.

The test case chosen for the development of REVER is the corpus of the pontifical documents and letters issued by the pontiffs and the papal chancery during the late Middle Ages. This corpus guarantees the presence of large collections of regesta and extended texts that were already edited and published in printed versions during the 19th and 20th centuries, such as Jaffé and Potthast's *Regesta Pontificum Romanorum*; the collection published by the *Bibliothèque des Écoles françaises d'Athènes et de Rome (BEF)*; the editorial series of the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica (MGH)*.

Those collections gathered all the documentation produced and issued by popes and pontifical chanceries – papal letters, bulls, decretals, etc. – from the origins of the Latin Church to the beginning of the 16th Century. Providing detailed records of papal decisions, letters, and administrative actions, they serve as a scholarly resource for the study of the Latin Church and, more broadly, for the history of ancient and mediaeval Europe. These collections of summaries of ancient documents have been compiled by intellectuals and scholars starting from the 19th century until the present, creating a remarkable corpus of historical data. However, only scanned versions of the *regesta* collections are available, not in machine-readable format. This occurs because this wealth of historical data is preserved in printed texts dating from the 19th and 20th centuries. The with fonts and layouts employed present a significant challenge for processing using traditional Optical Character Recognition (OCR) systems. In particular, *regesta* are characterised by a multi-column layout (which varies according to the edition in question), difficult-to-read ancient fonts, and an extensive use of abbreviations and acronyms.

The printed collections that were analysed and used for the creation of a training corpus for a generative AI specifically designed for summarisation are listed in the following table following the chronological order of the sources they edited (Tab. 1).

1.	Ph. Jaffé, <i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum usque ad annum 1198</i> . Primia ed Lipsiae 1851, secunda correctata et aucta auspiciis G. WATTENBACH, curaverunt S. LOEWENFELD, F. KALTENBRUNNER et P. EWALD, 2 vol. Lipsiae 1885/88
2.	A. Potthast, <i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum, 1198-1304</i> , 2 vol. Berlin, 1873/75
3.	P.F. Kehr, <i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum, Germania Pontificia</i> ed. A. BRACKMANN, 2 vol., Berlin 1911/35 (Italia Pont. 8 Vol. ibidem 1906/35)

4.	K. Rodenberg, <i>Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum</i> , Monumenta Germaniae Historica, 3 vols., 1883-1894
5.	P. Pressutti, <i>Regesta Honorii III</i> , 2 vol., Roma, 1888/95
6.	<i>Les Registres de Gregoire IX (1227/41)</i> ed. L. AUVRAY, (BEF), 3 tomi, Paris 1890/1918
7.	<i>Les Registres d'Innocent IV (1243/54)</i> , ed. E. BERGER (BEF), 4 tomi, Paris 1894
8.	<i>Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)</i> , ed. C. BOUREL, DE LA RONCIERE, J. DE LOYE, et A. COULON (BEF), 6 fasc., n. t., Paris
9.	<i>Les Registres d'Urbain IV (1261/64)</i> , ed. M. J. GUIRAUD (BEF), 12 fasc. sed absque indice, Paris
10.	<i>Les Registres de Clement IV (1265/68)</i> , ed. M. E. JORDAN (BEF), 6 fasc., n. t. Paris
11.	<i>Les Registres de Gregoire X et de Jean XXI (1271/77)</i> , ed. M. GUIRAUD et L. CADIER (BEF), 4 fasc. n. t. Paris
12.	<i>Les Registres de Nicolas III (1277/80)</i> , ed. M. J. GAY (BEF), 5 fasc. Paris, 1938
13.	<i>Les Registres de Martin IV (1281/85)</i> , ed. M. OLLIVIER-MARTIN (BEF), 3. fasc., Paris 1901/13
14.	<i>Les Registres de Honorius IV (1285/87)</i> , ed. M. PROU (BEF), 1 tome, Paris, 18
15.	<i>Les Registres de Nicolas IV (1288/92)</i> , ed. M.E. LANGLOIS (BEF), 9 fasc., Paris
16.	<i>Les Registres de Boniface VIII (1294-1303)</i> , ed. G. DIGARD, et alii (BEF), 17 fasc., Paris, 1939
17.	<i>Les Registres de Benoit XI (1303/04)</i> , ed. M. GRANDJEAN, 5 fasc. (BEF) Paris 1905
18.	<i>Regestum Clementis PP. V. (1305/14)</i> , ed. cura et studio monachorum O.S.B., 9 vol. 1 suppl., sed absque indice, Romae 1885 sq. (Table chronologique et Table des Incipit, ed. FAWTIER/LANHERS (BEF), Paris 1950
19.	<i>Lettres secretes et curiales du Pape Jean XXII (1316/34) relatives a la France</i> , ed. M.A. COULON (BEF), n. t. 5 fasc., Pari
20.	<i>Lettres communes du Pape Jean XXII</i> , ed. M.G. MOLLAT, 30 fasc. Paris 1905/47 (BEF)
21.	<i>Register des Gegenpapstes Nikolaus V (1328/30)</i> , ed. EUBEL in Arch. Zschr. 1893, pp. 123/212

22.	<i>Les Registres et Letters communes de Benoit XII (1334/42), ed. M. VIDAL (BEF), 6 fasc. Paris 1911</i>
23.	<i>Lettres closes de Benoit XII relatives a la France, ed. M.G. DAUMET (BEF), 3 fasc. Paris, 1913/50</i>
24.	<i>Lettres closes de Clement VI (1342/52) relatives a la France, ed. M. VIDAL (BEF), 5 fasc., Paris, n. t.</i>
25.	<i>Les Registres d'Innocent VI (1352/62), ed. M. DEPREZ (BEF), 1 fasc. n. t. Paris</i>
26.	<i>Lettres secretes d' Urbain V (1362/70) relatives a la France, 2 fasc. n. t., ed. P. LECASHEUX (BEF)</i>
27.	<i>Registres d'Urbain V (1362/70), 1 fasc., n. t., ed. M. DUBRULLE (BEF), Paris</i>
28.	<i>Les Registres de Gregoire XI (1370/78), ed. M. MIROT (BEF), 3 fasc., n. t. Paris</i>
29.	<i>Bullenregister Martin V, in MIÖG Ergbd. I (1885) 401 ff., 1894, 661 ff.</i>

Table 1

2. Corpus Analysis and Methodological Approach for REVER

2.1. Reverse Regesta and the Need for Text Recognition

As previously discussed, the primary challenge encountered by REVER was the definition of the textual corpus. Given the extensive duration of papal activity, the project faced a vast number of documents. Consequently, it was necessary to narrow the scope to a specific subset of data and volumes (refer to paragraph 1.3). The available collections of texts present considerable variability: some include both the regesta and the corresponding extended texts, while others, such as the *Regesta Pontificum Romanorum* (1874) edited by A. Potthast, consist solely of regesta with references to additional volumes containing the full documents (see paragraph 1.3).

The challenges in defining the corpus led to a preference for collections that include both the regesta and the extended texts. However, the total volume of documents and regesta remains significant, as all the printed materials need to be converted into machine-readable text.

A second critical issue was the necessity of obtaining plain text. Simple scans of volumes result in images of pages, which are insufficient for the marking processes required for summarization, which can only be performed on fully processed text. An additional step is therefore indispensable: transforming the scanned page images into digital text that can be searched, analyzed, and processed using computational tools (see fig. 1).

Document Scan Scanned image HTR Text

Figure 1: From printed editions to Plain Text

2.2. Field of Study: paleography and diplomatics

Paleography deals with the study of ancient manuscripts and their writing. This discipline involves reading, interpreting, and cataloguing historical documents. Its purpose is to interpret ancient manuscripts by providing useful elements for historical reconstruction and it is itself a form of historical research. Its primary objective is to provide critical insights for historical reconstruction, thereby constituting an indispensable component of historical research in its own right. With the advent of digital technologies, paleography has greatly benefited from advanced tools designed to decipher ancient texts, thereby opening new research perspectives and improving accessibility to historical documents.

While these tools cannot detect falsifications within the documents, they provide significant support for transcription, effectively recognizing texts in a multitude of languages and accommodating complex layouts.

Modern digital tools are capable of recognizing scripts written in both left-to-right and right-to-left orientations. Furthermore, they are capable of processing texts with complex graphical configurations, such as legal glosses (see fig. 2). Mastery of abbreviations is an indispensable skill in paleography, as abbreviations were widely employed in ancient manuscripts to conserve space—a necessity given the high cost of writing materials, which demanded their optimal use.

Figure 2: Layout Analysis.

An example of layout in legal glosses. Decretum Gratiani emendatum et notationibus illustratus una cum glossis, Gregorii XIII Pont. Max. iussu editum, Romae, in Aedibus Populi Romani, 1582 (thanks to Roberto Imperia for this excerpta).

Current OCR systems incorporate training mechanisms that allow the creation of models useful for automatically recognising abbreviations. The analysis of graphic characters and writing styles enables paleographers to ascertain the period during which a document was produced—a critical aspect, as the models developed through training can be tailored to specific historical periods or writing styles. These models can then be applied to similar types of texts, periods, or layouts. For an optical recognition system, there is no inherent distinction between a single-column page, a two-column page, or pages with marginal glosses. Consequently, it is mandatory that those responsible for OCR training possess the expertise to accurately identify the text structure and the distinctive characteristics of the writing.

Effective training facilitates the development of advanced recognition models capable of managing increasingly complex layouts and character sets. Alongside paleography, diplomatics plays a pivotal role in the analysis of archival material, as it supports the cataloguing of historical documents, thereby enhancing research and accessibility.

Text recognition grounded in palaeographic expertise is fundamental for numerous textual corpora within the ITSERR project, particularly for the WP REVER. Its primary

objective is to re-establish the connection between documents and their corresponding *regesta*.

2.3. Corpus definition and pre-processing methodology

A *corpus* is a collection of multiple texts, gathered and published with the aim of providing an ordered and complete series of writings. The characteristics that unify them are determined by the chosen selection criteria and the objectives of the text analysis itself. *Corpora* can pertain to one or more authors, may be defined according to chronological criteria, or may be constituted around specific subjects. In the case of the REVER, the corpus consists of a collection of *regesta* and medieval papal documents published by prominent scholars during the 19th and 20th century (see Table 1).

Once the corpus was defined, it was necessary to understand how to obtain machine-readable plain texts.

In the initial phase, we identified the edition of the *regesta* edited by Potthast (1874-1895), one of the most complete collections of *regesta*, summarizing the papal documents issued from 1198 to 1304.

Regesta pontificum romanorum, edited by August Potthast,
volume 1, Berlin, Rudolf de Decker, 1874

*Monumenta Germaniae
Historica (MGH)*
volume 1, Berlin,
Weidmannos, 1883

Figure 3: Two types of regesta editions

The *regestum*, as will be explained more extensively in the following paragraph, is a summary of the original document made for the use of stakeholders and scholars, allowing the content of the document to be readily available without needing to consult it in its entirety. As one can imagine, each *regestum* is accompanied by a document. One of the challenges encountered when attempting to retrieve data from a collection is that the regestum and the corresponding document are not contained within the same volume. (see fig. 3). The Potthast edition, for instance, consists solely of *regesta*, with the corresponding documents dispersed across a significant number of different volumes—approximately 850, as estimated. These 850 volumes encompass roughly 50,000 extended documents. In other words, the content of two volumes from the Potthast edition (spanning 1198 to 1304) corresponds to circa 50,000 extended texts, which are spread across 850 different volumes (see fig. 4). This distribution presented a significant challenge in terms of data management, which prompted us to revise our strategy while continuing work on the Potthast edition. The construction of the dataset based on Potthast’s volume presented a significant challenge: the retrieval of the full texts corresponding to the *regesta* compiled by Potthast. This task required a manual search, identification, and collation of the matching extended documents. It was therefore decided to rely on *regesta* collections that, although potentially less comprehensive from a chronological standpoint, included the corresponding critical editions of the full texts. This choice ensured a more efficient and reliable data acquisition workflow and enabled a more systematic construction of the training dataset.

Figure 4: The first model of data collection on papal regesta

Therefore, in a second phase the following editions has been then identified: a) the Berger's edition of 1897, consisting in 4 volumes; b) the Haluscynskij edition of 1962, 1 volume; c) the *regesta* contained in the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica*, of 1883-1894, from which we select the 3 volumes of the *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum romanorum*; d) the Auvray edition of 1890-1955, consisting in 4 volumes; and, finally, e) the 2 volumes of *regesta* edited by Potthast (1874-1895), (fig.6). Rather than adhering strictly to a chronological criterion, as initially planned, we chose thus to focus on the *regesta* related to the pontificates of Innocent IV and Gregory IX.

Figure 5: The second model of data collection on papal regesta

The second model of data collection on papal regesta. The refined model aims to facilitate the creation of a dataset that can be easily usable in the computer processing phases of the project. We have selected collections that include both the *regesta* and their corresponding extended texts.

In this new workflow, the first phase will involve the elaboration of machine-readable text extracted from the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica* (MGH).

In a third phase we will focus on the Auvray edition, paying particular attention to the quality of the printed edition and on the training of a Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) system calibrated for their specific type of layout. It will then follow the texts preparation of the editions of Berger and Haluscynskij as a basis to ensure that the *regesta* are accurately and consistently represented, thereby facilitating the subsequent integration of data into the project workflows.

Finally, the fourth phase will involve the Potthast *regesta*, which will be employed as the testing tool for the workflows developed in the previous two phases and – being the most comprehensive collection – it will serve as verification tool. Potthast will be thus used as an encyclopaedia of all existing medieval sources which need to be taken into account.

Adherence to this workflow will thus be possible to obtain approximately pairs of 1,500 *regesta* with the corresponding extended texts from the three volumes of the MGH; 112 *regesta* with the corresponding extended texts from the Haluscynskij edition; 8,350 *regesta* and the same number of extended texts from the Berger edition; 6,180 *regesta* with their corresponding extended texts from the Auvray edition; while from the Potthast edition, it will be possible to obtain 7,500 *regesta* without the extended texts of the Papal documents (Fig. 5). In this way, it will be possible to provide the computer scientists engaged in the machine learning process with an approximate total of 23,000 *regesta*, accompanied by the corresponding to 23,000 extended texts.

If needed, the tested procedure will be then applied to all the others existing collections of pontifical documents listed in Table 1.

3. Analysis of OCR and HTR existing tools

3.1. What is an Optical Character Recognition system

An Optical Character Recognition (OCR) system is a technology designed to recognize printed characters and convert them into a digital format. This system enables the transformation of text from physical or digital documents into machine-readable text, which can then be processed, searched, and modified. In essence, the term "OCR" encompasses all tools that facilitate the conversion of digitized objects into electronic text (see fig. 6) or, more broadly, into a format that can be processed by a computer (i.e. .txt, .doc, .pdf, .xml formats).

Figure 6: The transformation through an OCR System

Nevertheless, OCR encounters some challenges with handwritten texts, imperfect paper prints, certain types of layouts, ancient languages, and less common characters. Ink stains left by typographic printing are often mistaken for symbols and interpreted as punctuation marks or numbers. Blurry digits are sometimes confused with others, such as "2" and "9", or "1" and "7". The letter "e" is often mistaken for "c". The ancient long form of the letter "s" is frequently interpreted as "f" (fig. 8).

Figure 7: Typographical critical elements

Faded letters may not be recognized or are transcribed with incorrect or out-of-context symbols. Specialized software is required to address these challenges and streamline the workflow for processing large volumes of documents and their corresponding *regesta*. The presence of special characters—such as diphthongs, word abbreviations, ink degradation over time, and blurred backgrounds—further complicates the recognition process. Additionally, the use of Latin in *regesta* and papal documents increases the difficulty of optical recognition. For alphabetic systems such as Greek, Arabic, Hebrew, Coptic, or Church Slavonic, OCR models are still under development. Further challenges arise from the orientation of writing, whether left to right, right to left, or vertical.

3.2. What is an Handwritten Text Recognition Systems

There are two primary types of automatic text recognition: OCR, which focuses on printed characters, and HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition), which deals with handwritten text. OCR is a standardised technology that is capable of recognizing text without the necessity of prior training, as it already contains predefined models of the letters it is intended to identify.

This technology is best suited for printed texts but less effective when used with manuscripts or ancient prints, for which HTR is a more appropriate choice. Unlike OCR, HTR does not rely on predefined letter shapes; instead, it accommodates the variability inherent in different handwriting styles. Consequently, HTR uses neural networks that are trained with sample data, learning to recognize letters and words specific to a particular handwriting style. In most cases, HTR requires training, given the complexity of the task it addresses.

3.3. Basic OCR-HTR glossary

- **Area:** in the context of an OCR system, an area is a defined portion of a document that contains text or other visual elements to be recognized. It can be a bordered area that contains a column of text, a paragraph, a block of images, a table, or any other distinctive component of the document layout. The area is important for facilitating the recognition of text or the classification of elements of interest, thereby improving the accuracy of the OCR process.
- **Region:** a region is a specific area of a digital image containing text that needs to be recognized and processed. Regions can be defined based on the structure of the document and often include blocks of text, headings, paragraphs, tables, or other visual elements. Dividing the content into regions helps the OCR system correctly identify where the different parts of the textual content are located and handle them separately for more accurate recognition.
- **Segmentation:** segmentation is the process of dividing a digital image containing text into smaller, recognizable units, such as blocks of text, lines, and individual characters. This step enables the correct identification of the various components in the document and allows the OCR system to process and recognize the text accurately. Segmentation can involve lines or regions: region-level segmentation separates blocks of text, images, tables, or other layout elements; line-level segmentation divides the text into lines
- **Binarization:** binarization is the process of converting a grayscale (or colour) image into a binary image, where each pixel is represented by one of two values: typically 0 or 1, black or white. This process simplifies the image by emphasizing the contrast between the text and the background, making it easier for algorithms to identify and extract the text. By reducing the image to two colours, binarization helps improve the accuracy of text recognition and other image processing tasks.
- **Recognition:** recognition refers to the process of identifying and interpreting characters, words, and symbols from images. This process transforms these images into machine-readable text, enabling applications such as document digitization, data entry automation, and text search capabilities.
- **Noise:** noise is a set of unwanted signs and consists of random imperfections in color or brightness of the digitized images (fig. 9).

Figure 8: Examples of noise

4. Common Elements of OCR and HTR Systems

Different kinds of OCR-HTR systems for the recognition of pre-modern handwritten texts present some common steps. This offers a considerable advantage because the training of new domain experts can rely on common concepts that remain identical regardless of the system in use: areas, regions, lines, segmentation, recognition, binarization.

4.1. Core Phases of OCR/HTR Systems

A. Pre-processing

- Input preparation: the page must be converted into a format compatible with the OCR-HTR system
- Page noise removal: image cleaning also includes optimization and binarization, the process that translates the various colour tones of the image into a distinct black and white one.

B. Segmentation

- Region segmentation, i.e., parts of the page to be transcribed
- Line segmentation, i.e., recognizing the lines in which the text is organised

C. Recognition

- Text recognition: i.e., transcription of symbols into digital text
- Output in various formats

The outputs must subsequently be examined by a domain expert, who evaluates the accuracy and reliability of the transcription. This verification step is essential for identifying potential errors or systematic weaknesses in the processing pipeline. Depending on the findings, the scholar may decide to adjust system parameters or refine the training corpus employed during the pre-processing, segmentation, and text-recognition stages. Such iterative revision enables the continuous optimisation of the workflow and the progressive improvement of transcription quality.

4.2. Operational Phases of OCR/HTR Software

As mentioned earlier, text recognition in OCR/HTR operates on two main levels: segmentation and character recognition. OCR/HTR segmentation divides an image containing text into separate structural units. There are two main types of

segmentation: by regions and by lines. Region segmentation refers to distinct parts of the text, such as paragraphs, columns, notes, and glosses. Line segmentation identifies text lines, which, in manuscripts and ancient prints, often appear fragmented, exhibit discontinuous colour, or are altered by handwriting irregularities or printing defects. For pre-modern texts with significant noise, such as background defects, text recognition is preceded by an image optimization phase to improve character readability and make text regions and lines more evident. In some OCR/HTR systems, binarization - the process that converts a colour or grayscale image into a black-and-white one - is applied. This step, combined with noise removal, is essential for accurate recognition (fig 10). Initially, the software identifies regions, meaning the layout structure and text orientation, before moving on to recognizing text lines.

Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR)

Preprocessing

Segmentation

Recognition

Figure 9: The three phases of OCR-HTR system

Text layout can create interpretation challenges, especially when it deviates from the common arrangement of one or two columns. Even if the algorithm can recognize individual characters, it may have difficulty with the overall structure. Text recognition involves multiple processes, addressing both the structure of the text and the characters themselves. In some cases, words and letters may be correctly recognized but placed in the wrong position. Alternatively, meaningless or grammatically incorrect words might be generated, but placed in the correct position. It's important to emphasize that both, layout and character recognition systems, are fundamental for the effective functioning of an OCR/HTR system.

Regions and lines segmentation is a key operation that helps overcome many challenges in interpreting the text. Specific OCR/HTR software includes a segmentation adjustment system that allows domain experts to reorder line sequences, correct broken lines, and interpret complex layouts that would otherwise hinder text recognition. After noise removal and region and line segmentation, the digital image is ready to be processed by text recognition models.

4.3. Manual and Automatic Workflow

It is first necessary to ensure that the text image to be recognised has been prepared correctly. OCR/HTR systems are not compatible with all formats, making it essential to understand the required characteristics for accurate document digitization. Generally, most software can process images in common formats such as .jpg, however input format compatibility represent a critical consideration. OCR systems convert image files—such as those in .jpeg, .png, .bmp, or .tiff formats—into text-based formats like .txt, .doc, .pdf, or .xml (see figs. 6 and 7).

Equally important is knowledge of output formats, as they influence the possibilities for subsequent text processing and AI training. In general, the steps involved in text recognition processes are consistent across systems. The process begins with page preparation, which includes converting the document into a compatible format and, often, removing digital noise. Noise consists of unwanted artifacts, such as random imperfections in color or brightness. It may result from image acquisition errors, mechanical imperfections in printing processes, ink smudges, or electronic noise introduced during scanning.

Once the image is optimised, the next step is segmentation, which divides the text image into regions and lines to facilitate recognition. Advanced recognition software often allows users to interact with both text region and line segmentation. Here, human

intervention and the expertise of scholars are indispensable for developing interpretative models that can be saved, adapted, and improved over time.

Some software also enables users to delineate specific areas of the image for targeted processing. This functionality is particularly useful for documents with complex layouts, such as medieval legal glosses (see figs. 2 and 10), biblical commentaries, or texts containing marginal notes. Corrections to text layout can be performed manually, and these adjustments can contribute to the training of models capable of recognizing regions, lines, and areas. Through such training, specific segmentation models can be developed and applied to similar types of documents.

Both segmentation and text recognition models play a crucial role in achieving high-quality results, as the outcome largely depends on the quality of the underlying model. After segmentation, text recognition may proceed in two ways: either through manual transcription or by applying an existing model, which can be further trained to enhance its capabilities. If an existing model is used, transcription errors can be corrected directly within the text. Finally, different software tools produce various output formats; among these, full-text and PDF formats are often the most versatile for further processing and analysis.

5. Analysis of OCR-HTR systems: features, capabilities, and key criteria

5.1. Tested Softwares

To understand the best solution for our work, we tested a series of software applications and classified their characteristics. The software considered and tested include: *Treventus*, *Transkribus*, *OCR4all*, *Chat GPT*, *Rescribe*, and *Escriptorium*. All these tools create workflows and are based on systems such as Kraken, ScanTailor, Larex, Tesseract, and others.

- *Treventus* is not strictly an OCR system but a high-speed scanner that includes software called ScanGate, which enables the conversion of paper documents into plain text files. The input formats are JPEG, TIFF, PNG, GIF, and BMP. It provides outputs in JPEG, TIFF, PNG, GIF, BMP, HOCR and PDF formats.
- *Transkribus* (Fig. 11) is a tool that uses AI and ML algorithms to transcribe and digitise any type of handwritten or printed document. It can train its capabilities through machine learning models. The input formats supported are JPG, PNG, and PDF. It provides output in the following export formats: PDF, TXT, XML, DOCX, Excel/CSV, ALTO XML, and TEI.

Figure 10: Transkribus interface

- **OCR4all** (Fig. 12) uses various open-source tools to automate the recognition of text in historical prints. It uses Larex for segmentation and Calamari for character recognition. The input formats are PNG and PDF. It provides output in TXT, XML, and DOCX formats.

Figure 11: OCR4all Interface

- **Rescribe** (Fig. 13) is an OCR software for historical texts designed for Tesseract and OCRopus engines. The input format is PDF, and it provides output in PDF.

Figure 12: Rescribe Interface

- **Escriptorium** (Fig. 14) is a system for analysing printed and handwritten texts that uses machine learning techniques. *Escriptorium* can recognize and interpret various types of characters. It also has a training function. The input formats are JPG, PNG, GIF, TIFF, and BMP. It provides output in ALTO, TXT, and Page formats. It uses Kraken as engine and it is an open source project.

Figure 13: Escriptorium Interface

Tesseract	ABBYY Fine Reader
open access	proprietary software
Windows, Linux, MacOS	Windows, Linux, MacOS
recognition: isolated characters	recognition: isolated characters
output: .txt .doc .pdf .xml .html	output: .txt .doc .pdf .xml .html

Table 2: The most popular OCR software

Rescribe	Escriptorium
open access	open access
Windows, Linux, MacOS	Windows, Linux, MacOS
It is not possible to interact with the models	Use and creation of models
output: .txt .doc .pdf .xml .html	output: .txt .xml

Table 3: HTR handwritten text recognition for historical texts

5.2. The choice the Right OCR-HTR

The operation of recognizing ancient prints is, in many ways, similar to recognizing handwritten text (HTR). Since the number of documents and regesta to be processed is very high, the working group deemed it necessary to test various recognition systems in order to evaluate how to work in a simple, effective, and fast way.

5.3. Considered criteria for evaluation

1. Compatibility with operating systems: We evaluated the compatibility of the OCR software with common operating systems such as Windows, macOS, and Linux.
2. Online/offline operations: We assessed whether the OCR software can be used online or requires offline installation.
3. Free or paid licence: We checked whether the OCR software is free or requires payment.
4. Ease of use: We evaluated the user-friendliness of the OCR software interface and its overall ease of use.
5. Ability to recognize ancient print texts: We tested the OCR software's capability to accurately recognize text from historical documents and manuscripts.
6. Recognized languages: We verified which languages the OCR software supports, specifically testing its recognition accuracy for latin texts.
7. Character recognition quality: We evaluated the accuracy and quality of character recognition performed by the OCR software.

8. Use of uploaded images for training of shared application models: We examined whether the OCR software retains the images for further training purposes to prevent copyright issues.
9. Type of Output Produced: We reviewed the types of output formats supported by the OCR software, such as TXT, DOCX, PDF, etc., and evaluated their appropriateness for computer processing and analysis.
10. Training Process: We examined the training capabilities based on the specific layout model present in the text to be digitised.

SOFTWARE	INPUT	OUTPUT	TOOLS
Treventus	paper pages	pdf e hocr	Scan Gate
Transkribus	jpg, png, pdf	pdf, txt, xml, docx, excel/csv, tei export	Pylaia
OCR4all	png, pdf	txt, xml, docx	Larex, Calamari
Chat GPT 4.0	pdf, jpeg, gif, tiff, bmp, png, nef, arw, psd, raf, tiff, heif, svg	unable to directly generate output files like text documents or download files	unknow
Rescribe	pdf	pdf	Tesseract, Ocropus
Escriptorium	jpg, png, gif, tif, bmp	alto, text, page	Kraken

Table 4: Overview of the analysed Optical Recognition Systems

6. Results

The existing OCR and HTR systems have therefore features that make them suitable for processing different text types, depending also on the specific needs of each research group. A preliminary analysis is therefore necessary for the start of any collection of historical data from printed texts.

Ultimately, REVER has chosen to use a local instance of EScriptorium, thanks to the collaboration with the CNR and the creators of the Software.

The pre-processing of the text corpus outlined so far has enabled the creation of a large text corpus, which is fundamental for the design and training of the REVER tool. The workflow and standards that have been established will also permit the enlargement of the corpus of texts and thus strengthen the training and testing activities.

The case of the *regesta* collections, as seen, presented several challenges, especially with regard to the transformation of digitised documents from images to plain text. Indeed, these printed editions are characterised by a complex layout (often multi-column), the presence of ancient characters (with complex bindings) and the use of numerous acronyms. At the same time, these characteristics are peculiar to this type of text, which thanks to its layout and the use of abbreviations and technical language is quick and easy to consult.

Characteristics and challenges that closely resemble those encountered in the digitisation of manuscripts and early printed works. For this reason, dedicated HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition) software solutions were employed to address these complexities effectively.

Moreover, the work realised for the corpus preparation can also be adopted by those who would like to prepare different texts to use our REVER tool.

In light of the considerations outlined above, it was decided to proceed by testing various existing and freely accessible tools, examining the advantages and limitations of each tool, in order to provide valid guidelines for processing corpora with different characteristics, both in terms of layout and content.

7. Acronyms

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
IB	ITSERR Board
ITSERR	Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE
LM	Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca
OU	Organisational Unit
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PI	Principal Investigator
PLA	Performance Level Agreement